

REQUIREMENTS FOR TEACHERS IN ORGANIZING LITERATURE LESSONS BASED ON MODERN APPROACHES

Abdullayeva Maftuna Odiljon kizi

Independent researcher at Gulistan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14547115>

Abstract: The article discusses the requirements for a teacher in organizing literature lessons based on modern approaches, and what the components of a teacher should consist of.

Keywords: flexibility, trust, communication, innovation, organization, online platform, social network, modern teacher, creativity.

Introduction

Currently, great changes are taking place in the field of literature. Organizing literature lessons based on modern approaches ensures that the lessons are richer, more meaningful, more interesting, and more effective. The current development of literature is determined by a number of factors. Among these factors, technological changes, social networks, globalization, and the processes of creating new genres play an important role. A teacher must have many abilities in addition to his specialty. That is, he must have high professional training, high moral qualities, have a special education, and be a person who can work in educational institutions.

Methodology

Through technological changes, the Internet and digital technologies have changed the distribution and consumption of literature. E-books, audiobooks, and online platforms (e.g., Wattpad, Goodreads) allow a new generation of writers to present their works to a wide audience. With social media, writers can directly reach their fans through social media. This helps to get instant feedback on their work and develops interactive communication between authors and readers. With globalization, literature is transcending national borders and using the intersection of different cultures. Writers are translating works written in different languages, attracting new audiences. New genres and styles Experimental styles and genres are emerging in literature today. For example, new ideas and forms are emerging in areas such as fantasy, science fiction, and postmodernism. Social issues are being raised in contemporary literature through social issues, such as gender equality, racial equality, and environmental problems. Writers who cover these topics are attracting the attention of many people. In Uzbek literature, our writers are using innovative approaches to illuminate the problems of modern life. The activities of young writers are giving new opportunities to the development of literature in Uzbekistan. In general, it is clear that today literature is developing in new forms and its progress continues. This is of great importance for human culture.

Discussion

Today, the number of educators who take a modern, creative approach to teaching is increasing in the educational process. And for this, it is important for a teacher to have many skills. The following components should be well-formed in a modern educator:

1. Adaptability. In this modern, digital age, teachers must be flexible and able to adapt to anything. Whether it is the way students learn, classroom behavior, or lesson plans, being able to adapt is a skill that every modern teacher should have.

2. Confidence. Every teacher must demonstrate confidence not only in themselves, but also in their students and colleagues. A confident person inspires others to be confident in themselves, and a teacher's confidence helps others become better people.

3. Communication. Being able to communicate is an important skill, not only with students, but also with parents and staff. Think about it: a teacher spends almost their entire day interacting with students and colleagues, so it's important to be able to communicate clearly and concisely to get your point across.

4. Team Leader. Part of being a teacher is the ability to work together as part of a team or group. When you work together as a team, it gives students more opportunities to learn and have fun. Connecting with other teachers (even virtually) and solving problems together will only lead to success. It creates a sense of community not only in your classroom, but throughout the school.

5. Lifelong Learner. Teaching is a lifelong learning process. The world is always changing, along with the curriculum and educational technologies, so it's up to you, the teacher, to keep up. A teacher who is always willing to go the extra mile to learn will always be an effective and successful teacher.

6. Imagination. The most effective tool a teacher can use is their imagination. Teachers need to be creative and think of unique ways to engage their students in learning, especially now that many states have implemented the Common Core State Standards into their curricula. Many teachers feel that these standards take away all the creativity and fun from learning, so teachers are finding imaginative ways to make learning fun again.

7. Leadership. An effective teacher is a mentor and knows how to guide their students in the right direction. They are role models and role models. They motivate students and lead them to success.

8. Organization. Modern teachers have the ability to organize and prepare for the unknown. They are always ready for anything that is thrown their way. Should you go home sick? No problem, there's a replacement folder. Research shows that organized teachers create more effective learning environments. So, if you want to achieve high results, being organized is even more essential.

9. Innovation. The modern teacher is willing to try new things, from new educational apps to teaching skills and electronic devices. Being innovative means not only trying new things, but also asking your students questions, making real-world connections, and developing creative thinking. This encourages your students to take risks and learn to collaborate with others.

10. Commitment. While commitment is a traditional teaching skill, it's also a modern one. The modern teacher must always be engaged in their profession. Students need to feel that their teacher is ready for the lesson.

11. Online reputation management skills. This is the 21st century, and modern teaching skills are certainly new. In this digital age, most, if not all, teachers are online, meaning they have an "online reputation." Modern teachers need to know how to manage their online reputation and which social media platforms are appropriate for them to use.

LinkedIn is a professional social network for connecting with colleagues, but other social media profiles like Instagram or Facebook should be personal and separate from students.

12. Engagement skills. Modern teachers know how to find interesting resources. Finding materials and resources that interest students is crucial these days. This means staying up-to-date with new educational technologies and apps, browsing the internet, and connecting with other teachers. In any case, it's important to engage students and keep things interesting.

13. Technological skills. Technology is evolving rapidly. We have seen tremendous progress in the past five years and we continue to see it grow. While it can be difficult to keep up with these changes, it is something that all modern teachers must do. You not only need to understand the latest technologies, but you also need to know which digital tools are right for your students. This can be a process that takes time, but it has a huge impact on student success.

14. Know when to unplug. Modern teachers know when it is time to unplug from social media and just relax. They also understand that teacher burnout is high, so it is even more important for them to slow down and take care of themselves. They also know when it is time to tell their students to unplug and slow down. They give their students time every day for brain breaks and allow them to relax.

15. The ability to delegate. Teachers inspire; this is just one of the qualities that goes with the name. Modern teachers have the ability to make students think critically, innovatively, creatively, flexibly, enthusiastically and adaptively. They provide students with the opportunity to solve problems, self-manage, self-reflect and lead. They give them the tools to succeed not only in school, but also in life.

Many requirements are placed on the teacher when organizing literature lessons based on modern approaches. When using innovative methods, the teacher should use modern educational technologies, such as interactive teaching methods, game elements and project-based learning. It is important to take into account the opinions, feelings and experiences of students in the lesson process by encouraging active participation of students, giving them the opportunity to think independently. With a differentiated approach, it is important to take into account the individual characteristics of each student, assign tasks at different levels and organize lessons adapted to the abilities of each student. It is necessary to connect literature lessons with other subjects based on an interdisciplinary approach and provide students with knowledge in a broader context. It is necessary to provide students with the opportunity to analyze their work through self-assessment and reflection and create an environment that encourages their thoughts. Using modern information technologies (for example, Internet resources, e-books, multimedia materials) in the use of technology, lessons can be made more interesting and interactive. It is necessary to introduce students to cultural values through literature and develop their aesthetic feelings. Being a role model as a teacher, the knowledge, creativity and personal approach of the teacher should be an example for students. These requirements help to improve the professional qualifications of the teacher and serve to organize literature lessons more effectively.

Conclusion

When using innovative methods, it is necessary for the teacher to be able to effectively use modern teaching methods and technologies (for example, interactive learning, project-based

learning, cooperative learning). Individual assessment of students and assignment of tasks that correspond to their abilities ensures the personal development of each student. Activities aimed at developing critical thinking, analysis, and independent decision-making skills are organized in students. Literature lessons increase students' interest in literature by discussing topics related to modern life and culture. The active participation of students is ensured by using interactive methods such as discussion, role-playing games, and group work during the lesson. After the lesson, the teacher should analyze his/her activities and develop recommendations for improving future lessons. A more enriched learning environment can be created by integrating literature lessons with other subjects (for example, history, art, psychology). The use of digital tools in teaching (e-books, online platforms) increases the opportunity to organize the teaching process more effectively and interestingly.

References:

1. Azimova T. Pedagogik-psixologik tashxis va uning o'quv jarayonidagi ahamiyati. – Toshkent. 2017.
2. Ziyamammedov B. Pedagogika. – Toshkent. 2014.
3. Nuraliyev Sh. PEDAGOG SHAXSI VA UNGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 8 | 2021 ISSN: 2181-1601
4. Mirzayeva S.T. ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA ADABIY TA'LIMNI TASHKIL ETISH MEXANIZMLARI. INTER EDUCATION & GLOBAL STUDY. Ilmiy-nazariy va metodik jurnal, ISSN 2992-9024 (online) 2024, №4 (2).
6. Abdullayeva M.O. Adabiyot darslarini zamonaviy yondashuvlar asosida tashkil etish zarurati. Yosh olimlar axborotnomasi. Maxsus son, 4 (2023), ISSN 2181-5186, 70-73-betlar.
7. Abdullayeva M.O. Adabiyot darslarini tashkil etishda PISA xalqaro baholash dasturining ahamiyati. "Ilm-fan va innovatsiya: muammolar, yechimlar va istiqbollar" xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya, 2024-yil, 17-18-may, 268-272-b.
8. Abdullayeva O.O. Bo'lajak pedagoglarda tadqiqotchilik ko'nikmasini shakllantirishning nazariy asoslari // Kasb-hunar ta'limi №6, 2024. 97-100-betlar
9. Jo'rayev, S., & Abdurasulov, J. (2023). SUBJECT, TASKS AND CONTENT OF STUDYING THE BASICS OF MILITARY-PATRIOTIC EDUCATION. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(7), 149-153.
10. Abdurasulov J. (2024). HARBIY PEDAGOGIKANING BOSHQA FANLAR BILAN ALOQASI. Молодые ученые, 2(6), 48-52. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/yo/article/view/28164>
11. Abdullaeva, O. (2024). REQUIREMENTS FOR PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS IN PREPARING FOR SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY. В INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (Т. 4, Выпуск 12, сс. 306-308). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14539093>